

Theory of Quantum Control Systems, an Hypothesis

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Abstract—A frameworks of quantum control system explores feedback control which conceals error that will be eventually computed by quantum error correction at final stage of qubits to alter Quantum Control System.

Index Terms—Quantum Frameworks, Bloch Sphere, Quantum Error Correction.

I. INTRODUCTION

Draft of Quantum Control System follows a paradigm to act as interface between quantum frame works i.e, System Control, Qubit Control, Qubit Readout, Quantum Feedback. firstly system control is mechanism of quantum systems to specific states which involves in no feedback control or feedback control that continuously quantifies output with reference to desired setpoint and make necessary adjustment to **conceal error**. secondly, Qubit control means to control the quantum state of Qubits using electrical pulse i.e, external signal with reference to determining probability amplitude of desired states of qubits which is achieved by applying precise control pulse for superposition of $|1\rangle$ and $|0\rangle$ states within Bloch Sphere.

Fig. 1. Superposition of quantum states within Bloch Sphere

a) : Quantum readout determines final stage of qubits after performing quantum computation that follows performing quantum error correction and finally quantum feedback, unlike classical feedback loops this one introduces classical information that can alter the state of quantum system.

II. APPLICATION OF QUANTUM CONTROL SYSTEMS

Out of all existing applications, we prefer quantum computing which falls in our field of expertise and moreover its principles are based on high fidelity operations for performing quantum computing using qubits. Based on observations and

through controlling quantum control systems we intend to abide the fundamentals of quantum mechanics.

III. CONCLUSION

Either, Superposition of desired Quantum States with Bloch sphere for any 3 dimensional space or Qubit control driven by electrical pulse as cited at. el, [2], we conclude that Quantum error correction is driven by our previous research i.e, spatial entropy cited et.al, [1]

REFERENCES

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